

Electromagnetic Rail Lunar Launch System (EMRLLS): Architecture and Performance Trade Space for Lunar-Surface-to-Orbit Logistics

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Abstract

Sustained lunar operations will require surface-to-orbit logistics architectures that reduce dependence on consumable chemical propulsion. Electromagnetic launch concepts, including mass drivers and rail-based accelerators, have long been proposed as alternatives for transporting material from planetary surfaces without recurring need for propellants. This study develops a foundational systems framework that integrates electromagnetic launch scaling with lunar surface power generation, infrastructure sizing, and orbital retrieval logistics. The reference architecture analyzed in this work is referred to as the Electromagnetic Rail Lunar Launch System (EMRLLS).

The proposed architecture converts steady-state surface electrical generation into impulsive kinetic energy using buffered energy storage and controlled electromagnetic acceleration along a fixed, modular surface rail. The architecture consists of prime power generation, energy buffering, pulse conditioning, switching networks, launch track hardware, and thermal management subsystems. Through lumped-parameter analytical modeling, relationships are derived linking essential variables such as payload mass, allowable acceleration, rail length and terminal inclination, exit velocity, aggregate efficiency, peak power, and operational cadence. Computational trade studies using MATLAB and Python evaluate the resulting parameter space and inform the scaling relationships.

For representative payload classes in the 50–150 kg range and injection velocities consistent with an approximate 60 km circular lunar orbit ($\sim 1.65 \text{ km s}^{-1}$), the electrical energy required per launch falls between 100–300 MJ, assuming moderate efficiency. Scaling analysis indicates that exit velocity and aggregate system efficiency dominate infrastructure sizing, while thermal rejection frequently limits the sustainable launch cadence during high-current pulsed operations. These findings establish an initial set of feasibility boundaries for electromagnetic surface launch systems that support lunar surface-to-orbit logistics. The analytical framework offers a scalable engineering foundation for evaluating electromagnetic launch infrastructure within emerging lunar logistics architectures.

1. Introduction

Achieving a continuous lunar presence will require surface-to-orbit logistics architectures significantly different from the chemically dominated systems used for early exploration. Although chemical propulsion remains indispensable for launching from Earth and conducting high-energy maneuvers, its reliance on consumable propellant introduces structural inefficiencies for routine transportation between the lunar surface and orbit. As surface operations expand to support scientific research, habitation, manufacturing, and in situ resource utilization (ISRU), logistics cadence, reliability, and throughput become primary system constraints.

Electromagnetic launch systems, like mass drivers and rail-based accelerators, have long been considered promising alternatives to propellant-dependent transport methods for lunar and planetary applications. Early research explored the use of electromagnetic mass drivers to transport bulk material from the lunar surface and orbit, supporting the development of space-based industrial infrastructure (O'Neill, 1976; O'Neill et al., 1979). These concepts proposed the construction of large electromagnetic accelerators capable of launching processed materials or lunar regolith at high velocity while minimizing the need for additional propellant.

Later studies have investigated a range of electromagnetic launch technologies, including railguns, coilguns, and inductive mass drivers, for both space launches and high-velocity payload acceleration (Fair, 2007; McNab, 2003). Recent research has revisited these electromagnetic launch concepts with a focus on maximizing lunar resource utilization and facilitating large-scale material transport. This includes examining high-throughput mass drivers capable of launching bulk materials from the lunar surface at velocities sufficient to support orbital infrastructure and deep-space resource supply chains. These systems are generally designed to handle large payloads or raw materials with minimal sensitivity to acceleration loads, often assuming they will carry rugged bulk cargo such as regolith or processed feedstock.

The Electromagnetic Rail Lunar Launch System (EMRLLS) examined in this study is a logistics-oriented system designed to support sustained cargo transport from the lunar surface to low lunar orbit (LLO). The system uses electromagnetic launch infrastructure to convert the steady-state electrical power generated on the lunar surface into a steady throughput of payloads sent to orbit. EMRLLS achieves this by using buffered energy storage and pulsed electromagnetic acceleration along a fixed surface rail, effectively launching individual payloads into LLO for retrieval by orbital transfer systems.

Conceptually analogous to electromagnetic launch systems on Earth, the EMRLLS accelerates payloads along a surface rail using stored electrical energy, attaining sufficient velocity for insertion into LLO. First-order modeling suggests that payloads in the 100–300 kg class can be accelerated along a rail approximately 4 km in length to velocities near the circular orbital requirement for LLO.

The minimum injection velocity is determined by the circular orbital velocity at the target altitude. For a circular orbit at altitude h , the required velocity is given by

$$v_{orbit} = \sqrt{\frac{\mu_{moon}}{R_{moon}+h}} \quad (1)$$

where $\mu_{moon} = 4.904 \times 10^{12} \text{ m}^3/\text{s}^2$ is the lunar gravitational parameter, $R_{moon} = 1,737 \text{ km}$ is the mean lunar radius, and h is the orbital altitude above the lunar surface. For a representative altitude of $h = 60 \text{ km}$, the required circular velocity is approximately $1,651 \text{ m s}^{-1}$.

In practice, the rail exit velocity must exceed this ideal circular value to account for factors like the finite-duration acceleration, gravitational losses during ascent, injection geometry, and targeting tolerances. The circular velocity provides the baseline for infrastructure sizing, while additional margin defines the bounded exit-velocity design range for the scaling analysis in this study.

Injection conditions ensure that the payload is lofted into a LLO with sufficient stability to remain on orbit for approximately 12–24 hours. This provides an operational retrieval window without requiring immediate capture. Within this interval, the payload remains within a bounded orbital corridor suitable for interception by an autonomous grapppler vehicle. The grapppler is expected to rendezvous with the payload, stabilize and capture it, and transfer the payload to a higher orbital staging platform or alternative orbital plane. This study considers orbital lifetime, capture timing, and injection accuracy as boundary conditions that determine the minimum required injection velocity and targeting precision for successful retrieval.

Chemical ascent systems scale exponentially with propellant mass, while EMRLLS scales with energy storage and power throughput. Instead of using propellant to boost additional propellant, EMRLLS utilizes reusable electrical infrastructure, including surface power generation, energy storage (e.g., supercapacitors or batteries), pulse-power conditioning, and rail acceleration hardware. The architecture is designed for pulse operation: energy is accumulated gradually and released in short, high-power discharge events. First-order calculations indicate that launch energies between 100–300 MJ per event are sufficient for representative payload classes assuming overall system efficiencies near 50%. With launch intervals of approximately 30 minutes, the recharge requirements correspond to photovoltaic (PV) surface areas of a few thousand square meters, which is relatively modest compared to utility-scale installations when normalized for duty cycle and solar flux.

When coupled with an orbital interception layer, electromagnetic surface launch converts steady-state power generation into sustained orbital mass throughput. Surface infrastructure determines launch cadence and energy accumulation, while orbital systems determine redistribution and staging. This shifts lunar logistics from being vehicle-centric ascent cycles to an emphasis on infrastructure-mediated energy conversion.

Site selection materially influences feasibility. In optimal locations, solar availability can reach 70–80% over a lunar month, particularly in polar regions (Ross et al., 2021). To maximize quasi-continuous solar illumination, EMRLLS installations should be placed on elevated ridges or crater rims within a few degrees of the lunar poles. Previous studies identify particularly favorable regions near the Shackleton–de Gerlache area at the South Pole, as well as rims near Peary, Whipple, and Hinshelwood craters at the North Pole (Pappa et al., 2019; Glaser et al., 2014). These locations offer extended solar exposure and proximity to permanently shadowed regions that could support future ISRU activities.

The absence of atmospheric drag simplifies ascent compared to terrestrial electromagnetic launch concepts, though it still poses challenges related to acceleration tolerance, structural loading, thermal management, regolith stability, and electromagnetic losses.

From a systems engineering perspective, EMRLLS represents modular lunar infrastructure adaptable across multiple payload classes. Acceleration tolerance is linked to rail length, peak current, pulse duration, and structural requirements, shaping the design parameters. The infrastructure can handle different payload classes: rugged cargo tolerating up to 40 g acceleration, standard hardware near 25 g, sensitive instrumentation near 15 g, and fragile or biological transport close to 10 g. These tolerance ranges define the stress trade space that will be analyzed further.

The objective of this study is to define a reference architecture based on fundamental physical principles and bounded engineering constraints. The analysis will formalize the principal parameter relationships that determine feasibility and create a scalable analytical framework for trade studies across payload mass, acceleration tolerance, rail geometry, energy storage, and operational cadence. This analysis identifies a clear first-order feasibility envelope for electromagnetic surface launch as part of a broader lunar logistics infrastructure. The scaling relationships presented in the following sections are based on the assumptions detailed in Section 2.

2. System Architecture

2.1 Architectural Overview

EMRLLS is a modular lunar surface infrastructure that converts steady-state electrical generation into controlled electromagnetic acceleration events. It consists of distinct subsystems for power generation, storage, pulse conditioning, switching, acceleration, thermal management, and supervisory control. This structure supports scalability across different payload classes, facilitates maintenance and fault isolation, and enables incremental expansion as lunar operations mature.

At the system level, EMRLLS includes a prime power subsystem, an energy buffering subsystem, a pulse forming network, a switching network, a launch track subsystem, a thermal and structural management subsystem, and an integrated control and diagnostics network. Energy is accumulated over minutes and discharged in milliseconds to seconds during launch. Generation capacity is based on recharge requirements, while energy buffers handle transient loads. Figure 1 illustrates the functional decomposition and subsystem interfaces.

Figure 1

Electromagnetic Rail Lunar Launch System (EMRLLS) High Level Functional Architecture

Note. Functional block definition diagram depicting subsystem decomposition and primary interfaces among power generation, energy storage, pulse conditioning, switching, launch track hardware, sensing and instrumentation, timing and sequence control, thermal management, and supporting civil and structural infrastructure.

2.2 Prime Power Subsystem

The prime power subsystem provides continuous electrical generation for energy recharge, control electronics, and thermal management. Generation capacity is sized to meet average recharge demand given previously by Eq. (2), $P_{avg} = \frac{E_{launch}}{\tau}$, where E_{launch} is energy per launch and τ is launch interval.

Under representative modeling conditions requiring hundreds of megajoules per launch at cadences measured in tens of minutes, the average power demand can be met by moderate PV systems or compact surface fission systems. PV arrays offer modularity and are suited for polar illumination regimes (Landis et al., 1990). Additionally, hybrid architectures incorporating surface nuclear power can improve reliability and resilience during periods of low light conditions. Further, isolating the power generation from the launch discharge subsystem helps prevent transient propagation affecting the power infrastructure.

A first-order estimate of the PV infrastructure power system required to sustain launch operations may be obtained by relating the electrical energy required per launch event to the recharge interval between launches:

$$P_{avg} = \frac{E_{launch}}{t_{cadence}} \quad (2)$$

where P_{avg} is the average electrical power required to sustain the launch cadence, E_{launch} is the electrical energy required per launch event, and $t_{cadence}$ is the recharge interval between launches.

For a representative operational scenario with $E_{launch} \approx 200$ MJ, and $t_{cadence} = 1800$ s, the resulting average power requirement is $P_{avg} \approx 1.11 \times 10^5$ W ≈ 111 kW.

The corresponding effective PV generating area may be estimated as

$$A_{PV} = \frac{P_{avg}}{\eta_{PV} \cdot f_{illum} \cdot \eta_{store} \cdot \eta_{pc} \cdot \eta_{env} \cdot S_{eff}} \quad (3)$$

where A_{PV} is the effective PV generation area and P_{avg} is the average electrical power required to sustain launch cadence. The parameter η_{PV} represents PV conversion efficiency, f_{illum} is the fractional illumination availability over the operational interval, η_{store} is storage round trip efficiency associated with the energy buffering system, and η_{pc} represents power conditioning and distribution efficiency.

The term η_{env} is an aggregate environmental derating factor accounting for temperature effects, dust accumulation, radiation-induced degradation of PV cells (Siva-Rodriquez & Li, 2024), long-term PV performance degradation (Jordan & Kurtz, 2012), micrometeoroid impacts, and reduced collection efficiency associated with low-elevation solar incidence at polar lunar sites (Glaser et al., 2014). The term S_{eff} represents the effective solar flux incident on the PV array and is defined as $S_{eff} = f_{illum} \cdot S$, where f_{illum} is the fractional illumination availability over the operational interval and S is the solar flux at lunar distance ($\approx 1,361$ W m⁻²).

For representative parameter values, the effective generating requirement ranges from several hundred square meters to approximately 1,000 m², depending on derating factors. This area is the minimum needed to support the specified launch cadence. Lunar power systems deployed near polar regions can benefit from extended sunlight, reaching over 70–80% of the lunar year, depending on local terrain geometry (Mazarico et al., 2011). However, the low angle of the Sun above the horizon reduces collection efficiency and requires careful orientation and placement of solar arrays.

The effective PV generating area calculated above is necessary for meeting the electrical power needs, but it does not reflect the total footprint for the PV infrastructure. Practical deployments must also consider factors like array spacing, self-shadowing, terrain variability, segmentation for fault tolerance, survivability, and reserve capacity for evolving surface logistics operations. Therefore, the total installed PV field needed for sustained launch operations may approach about 2,000 m², aligning with the scale of surface electrical power infrastructure discussed in lunar exploration studies (Silva-Rodriguez & Li, 2024; Rose et al., 2021). A summary of the representative parameters used in the PV infrastructure estimate is provided in Table 1.

Table 1

Representative Parameters for Photovoltaic (PV) Infrastructure Estimate

Parameter	Representative Value	Description
E_{launch}	200 MJ	Electrical energy required per launch
$t_{cadence}$	1800 s	Recharge interval between launches
P_{avg}	111 kW	Average power required to sustain launch cadence
S	1361 W m ⁻²	Solar flux at lunar distance
η_{PV}	0.25	PV conversion efficiency
f_{illum}	0.75	Fractional illumination availability over 30 days
η_{store}	0.80	Storage round-trip efficiency
η_{pc}	0.90	Power conditioning and distribution efficiency
η_{env}	0.80	Environmental derating (dust, degradation, incidence)
M_{des}	1.8	Engineering design margin
A_{PV}	~2000 m ²	Estimated installed PV infrastructure

Note. Derating factors distinguish ideal PV conversion from delivered operational energy. The illumination fraction f_{illum} represents temporal solar availability, while η_{store} , η_{pc} , and η_{env} account for storage, power conditioning, and environmental losses. The design margin, M_{des} accounts for reserve capacity, redundancy, and operational growth.

2.3 Energy Buffering Subsystem

The energy buffering subsystem separates steady-state generation from pulsed discharge. It stores energy between launch events to meet the kinetic needs of the payload and account for conversion losses:

$$E_{\text{store}} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{mv^2}{\eta_{\text{sys}}} \quad (4)$$

where m is payload mass, v is rail exit velocity, and η_{sys} is the aggregate system efficiency.

Storage architectures can include high-discharge supercapacitor banks, high-rate battery modules, or hybridized configurations. Supercapacitors provide rapid discharge and long cycle life, while batteries offer higher energy density and recharge buffering. The subsystem cycles through controlled recharge, armed standby, discharge, and cooldown states. Continuous monitoring of state-of-charge, temperature, and electrical isolation is essential for operational safety and reliable performance.

2.4 Pulse Forming Network

The pulse forming network (PFN) conditions stored DC energy into a controlled current waveform compatible with rail and armature dynamics. It sets current rise time, matches impedance, and suppresses transients (Liebfried, 2017). Since electromagnetic force is proportional to the square of the current, stable waveforms are essential for uniform acceleration and consistent structural loading along the launch track. By separating energy storage from pulse shaping, waveforms can be adjusted without redesigning the primary storage or rail hardware. This modular approach allows for scalability across different payload classes. In this analysis, the PFN is treated functionally, emphasizing controlled energy delivery and hardware protection.

2.5 Switching Network

The switching network regulates pulse energy into discrete rail segments in a coordinated sequence. It must handle extreme transient currents while maintaining precise timing (Fair, 2007). By activating segmented rail sections, the system distributes electromagnetic forces evenly and reduces localized thermal stress on the launch track. The switching network not only manages gating but also arranges spatial sequencing. Additionally, it must rapidly isolate faults to prevent cascading failures and ensure a reliable open state after launch to eliminate residual conduction paths.

Switching technologies may include solid-state high-current devices, triggered vacuum switches, or hybrid configurations. The architectural requirement is precise high-current gating under pulsed conditions, while specific device implementation choices are beyond the focus of this work.

2.6 Launch Track Subsystem: Electromagnetic Rail Structure and Conduction Path

The launch track subsystem converts pulsed electrical energy into kinetic energy through electromagnetic interaction between parallel conductive rails and a translating armature or sabot assembly. A high-current pulse travels along the rails and through the armature, generating a magnetic field that produces a Lorentz

force, accelerating the payload along the guideway. This configuration enables direct electrical-to-mechanical energy conversion without chemical propulsion.

Selecting rail materials represents a trade between electrical conductivity and structural mass. High-conductivity materials like copper reduce resistive losses but add mass and deployment penalties, while aluminum offers lower mass but presents higher resistive losses. Hybrid or coated rail configurations may be employed to optimize efficiency with structural scalability.

Material selection is also constrained by ISRU considerations. Aluminum is more abundant in lunar regolith, while copper is scarce, favoring aluminum or hybrid rail architectures to reduce dependence on Earth-supplied materials. Aluminum-bearing phases constitute approximately 10-28 wt% (as Al_2O_3) in lunar regolith, compared to copper trace levels ($\sim 1-20$ ppm), supporting aluminum-dominant infrastructure approaches for scalable ISRU (Anand et al., 2012; Heiken et al., 1991).

The required rail length follows directly from constant-acceleration kinematics and is determined by the exit velocity requirement and allowable payload acceleration. Rail length is computed using Eq. (5)

$$L = \frac{v^2}{2a} \quad (5)$$

where v is the required exit velocity and a is the maximum acceleration allowed by the payload.

Acceleration tolerance impacts the infrastructure footprint. Lower tolerances require longer rail length, while higher tolerances lead to increased peak current demand and structural stress.

While the lunar environment eliminates atmospheric drag, it introduces additional engineering challenges, including variable regolith bearing capacity, thermal expansion cycling, and electrostatic dust transport. Structural supports must maintain alignment tolerances under electromagnetic recoil forces, while modular construction enables efficient replacement of high-wear components.

2.7 Thermal and Structural Management

Electromagnetic acceleration produces resistive and switching losses that generate heat. These losses are proportional to the integral of current squared over resistance:

$$Q_{loss} = \int I^2 R dt \quad (6)$$

where I is rail current and R is the effective electrical resistance of the current path, including rail and switching contributions (Bergman et al., 2018). Under high-current pulsed conditions, resistive heating increases quadratically with current amplitude, making the reduction of peak current an effective strategy for managing heat. Although individual launch events are short, cumulative heating limits the operational cadence. Thermal management has a greater impact on sustained throughput than peak power capability.

In a vacuum, heat rejection occurs primarily through radiation:

$$Q_{rad} = \epsilon\sigma A(T^4 - T_{env}^4) \quad (7)$$

where ϵ is radiator emissivity, σ is the Stefan–Boltzmann constant, A is effective radiative area, T is the radiator temperature, and T_{env} is the background temperature. Radiator sizing, emissivity, and permissible temperature rise determine the sustainable launch frequency. Additionally, structural factors also arise from electromagnetic recoil forces, rail deflection, and foundation loads. Cadence is therefore limited by thermal and structural considerations.

2.8 Control and Diagnostics Network

The control and diagnostics network manages subsystem operations and enforces safety interlocks. It monitors energy storage levels, rail temperature, switching status, environmental conditions, and projectile state. The system transitions through operational states including safe, charging, armed, firing, cooldown, and ready configurations based on subsystem health checks and threshold verifications.

The control layer integrates sensing with launch authorization logic to ensure energy availability, thermal margins, and subsystem integrity are verified before discharge. The analysis focuses on functional aspects of control, intentionally omitting specific algorithms, timing strategies, and implementation architectures.

2.9 Architectural Scaling Characteristics

The architecture demonstrates nonlinear scaling behavior across key parameters. Energy scales linearly with payload mass and quadratically with exit velocity. Rail length inversely relates to acceleration, while average power inversely relates to launch interval. Efficiency losses directly increase storage and generation requirements.

These relationships create a multidimensional trade space. The modular design allows for independent parametrization of generation, buffering, conditioning, switching, and acceleration functions within set constraints. EMRLLS is designed as a scalable lunar infrastructure that supports various mission classes within a cohesive engineering framework.

Section 3 details the physical and analytical relationships that define these connections.

3. Governing Physics and Analytical Performance Model

3.1 Modeling Philosophy and Scope

Section 2 establishes the functional elements of EMRLLS. This section details the physical relationships that determine subsystem sizing and operational limits. The analytical framework sets engineering feasibility boundaries, linking payload mass, acceleration tolerance, rail geometry, energy storage, power scaling, and operational cadence.

The framework utilizes a lumped-parameter model to focus on dominant energy and momentum relationships while clearly illustrating how design variables affect infrastructure requirements. It assumes vacuum operation, launching from the lunar surface with negligible initial horizontal velocity, and

transitioning into a circular lunar orbit. Acceleration is viewed as segmented and electromagnetic, while system efficiency is constrained within realistic engineering limits. All parameter definitions are based on assumptions introduced in Section 1.

3.2 Orbital Velocity Requirement

To achieve a circular orbit at altitude h above the lunar surface, the required orbital velocity can be calculated using the standard orbital velocity relation given in Eq. (1), $v_{orb} = \sqrt{\frac{\mu_{moon}}{R_{moon}+h}}$ (Bate et al., 2020). Here v_{orb} is the orbital velocity, $\mu_{moon} = 4.9048695 \times 10^{12} \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-2}$ is the gravitational parameter, and $R_{moon} \approx 1.737 \times 10^6 \text{ m}$ is the mean lunar radius. For an orbital altitude of $h = 60 \text{ km}$, the resulting velocity is approximately $1,650 \text{ m s}^{-1}$.

This value sets the baseline rail exit velocity required for achieving a circular orbit at the specified lunar altitude. In practice, additional velocity margin is necessary to accommodate finite-duration acceleration, gravitational losses during ascent, and targeting tolerances. The circular orbit velocity serves as a reference point for defining a bounded design range for rail exit velocity, which informs the sizing of energy storage, rail length, and power subsystems.

3.3 Rail Kinematics and Acceleration Constraints

Under the assumption of constant acceleration a along rail length L , kinematic relationships are determined by Eq. (5) $L = \frac{v_{exit}^2}{2a}$. Acceleration tolerance is expressed in multiples of standard Earth gravity as $a = ng_0$, where n represents the acceleration multiple in Earth-g units.

In the present study, n ranges from 10-40, corresponding to acceleration levels of 10-40 g (Earth gravity equivalent). While lunar gravity, g_{moon} , affects orbital dynamics and structural loads, it does not directly influence acceleration along the rail.

Rail length therefore scales inversely with acceleration, $L \propto \frac{1}{a}$. A lower acceleration tolerance increases corridor length and infrastructure footprint, while higher acceleration reduces rail length but increases peak electrical and structural loading. The time under acceleration can be calculated as:

$$t_{accel} = \frac{v_{exit}}{a}. \quad (8)$$

This pulse duration impacts thermal load distribution. Consequently, acceleration tolerance becomes a primary infrastructure-scaling variable that connects payload limits to corridor geometry.

3.4 Kinetic Energy Requirement

The electrical storage requirement, as introduced in Section 2.3, comprises the payload's kinetic energy and system efficiency. The ideal kinetic energy imparted to the payload is given by:

$$E_k = \frac{1}{2}mv_{exit}^2 \quad (9)$$

where E_k is kinetic energy (in Joules) and m is payload mass (kg). The exit velocity used here is slightly lower than the circular orbit velocity discussed in Section 3.2. For calculation purposes, the exit velocity is taken to align with the orbital velocity requirement to establish the corresponding energy bound. For a 100 kg payload accelerated to $1,651 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, the resulting energy is approximately $E_k \approx 136 \text{ MJ}$. Accounting for aggregate efficiency η_{sys} , the electrical energy required per launch is:

$$E_{launch} = \frac{E_k}{\eta_{sys}}. \quad (10)$$

With $\eta_{sys} = 0.5$, electrical input energy per launch is approximately 272 MJ. This value sets the minimum energy storage requirement for each launch event and informs buffer sizing.

Energy requirements scale linearly with payload mass and quadratically with exit velocity, meaning that velocity has a disproportionately large impact on infrastructure sizing.

3.5 Power and Pulse Dynamics

Although total energy determines storage requirements, instantaneous power affects component stress. Under constant acceleration, instantaneous mechanical power increases linearly with velocity and reaches a maximum at rail exit:

$$P_{peak} = mav_{exit} \quad (11)$$

where P_{peak} = peak mechanical power (W). This peak power scales linearly with mass, acceleration, and exit velocity.

This relationship emphasizes the system's pulse-dominated nature. While average power may be in the low megawatt range, instantaneous power during launch can be orders of magnitude higher. This pulse-dominated regime shifts stress concentration towards switching networks, conductors, and thermal management subsystems, while generation capacity is aligned with cadence. These power levels remain within the operational range of modern pulsed power systems when decoupled from continuous generation constraints (Fair, 2007).

3.6 Resistive Loss and Efficiency

Resistive heating within rails and switching components is represented by Eq. (6), $Q_{loss} = \int I^2 R dt$, where Q_{loss} denotes resistive heat (J), I is the current (A), and R is the effective electrical resistance (Ω) of the conduction path. Loss mechanisms include rail resistance, armature contact resistance, switching conduction losses, and pulse-conditioning inefficiencies.

Aggregate system efficiency can be expressed as the product of subsystem efficiencies:

$$\eta_{sys} = \eta_{cond} \cdot \eta_{switch} \cdot \eta_{arm} \quad (12)$$

For first-order modeling, a realistic efficiency range of 30–70% captures engineering uncertainties.

3.7 Average Power and Cadence

The launch cadence determines the required average recharge power, calculated using Eq. (2), $P_{avg} = \frac{E_{launch}}{\tau_{cadence}}$, where P_{avg} is the average recharge power (W) and τ is the launch interval (s). For a 272 MJ launch at a 30-minute cadence, the required average power is ≈ 151 kW. An increase in cadence proportionally increases generation and buffering requirements. This illustrates a key architectural advantage that infrastructure scales with average power instead of instantaneous power.

However, to sustain operations, cumulative resistive heating must be managed through radiative heat rejection. Thermal equilibrium constrains maximum cadence and establishes a relationship between radiator size, emissivity, temperature rise, and achievable launch frequency.

If cumulative heat per shot is Q_{loss} , thermal equilibrium requires:

$$\frac{Q_{loss}}{\tau_{cadence}} = Q_{rad}. \quad (13)$$

3.8 Thermal Equilibrium

Having established the energy and cadence relationships, sustained operation requires that resistive heating be balanced by radiative rejection under lunar vacuum conditions. Heat generated per launch is determined by Eq. (6), $Q_{loss} = \int I^2 R dt$, where Q_{loss} is the resistive heat per launch (J), I is instantaneous current (A), R is the effective resistance of the current path (Ω), and t is time (s).

Radiative heat rejection in vacuum is described by the Stefan–Boltzmann law (Bergman et al., 2018):

$$Q_{rad} = \epsilon\sigma A(T^4 - T_{sink}^4) \quad (14)$$

where Q_{rad} is the radiative heat rejection rate (W), ϵ is radiator emissivity, σ is the Stefan–Boltzmann constant ($W m^{-2} K^{-4}$), A is the effective radiator area (m^2), T is the radiator temperature (K), and T_{sink} is the background sink temperature (K).

For sustained launch cadence, the following relationship must hold:

$$\frac{Q_{loss}}{\tau} \leq Q_{rad} \quad (15)$$

where τ is the launch interval. The capacity for thermal rejection limits achievable throughput, independent of electrical feasibility. Therefore, radiator area and operating temperature become principal determinants of sustainable launch cadence.

3.9 Scaling Behavior

The relationships derived in Sections 3.2-3.8 highlight dominant scaling constraints that impact infrastructure sizing and operating limits. Acceleration tolerance serves as a primary factor influencing both rail footprint and peak electrical stress in the pulsed launch system.

Key first-order relationships include:

- Energy scales linearly with payload mass and quadratically with rail exit velocity.
- Rail length scales inversely with acceleration.
- Peak power scales linearly with mass, acceleration, and velocity.
- Average power scales inversely with launch interval.
- Efficiency losses directly affect storage and generation requirements.

These results indicate that acceleration tolerance is a primary infrastructure-scaling variable, balancing physical footprint with peak electrical stress. Such couplings define the infrastructure limits for architectural refinement. The scaling relationships are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2

Scaling Relationships for Electromagnetic Rail Lunar Launch System (EMRLLS) Infrastructure Drivers

Variable Increased	Primary Effect	Secondary Impact
Payload mass	Energy = m	Storage and peak power increase
Exit velocity	Energy = v ²	Rail length and pulse stress increase
Acceleration	Rail length decreases	Peak power increases
Cadence	Avg power increases	Thermal margin decreases
Efficiency decreases	Storage requirement increases	PV area increases

Note. Scaling relationships follow directly from the expressions for payload kinetic energy

$$E_k = \frac{1}{2}mv_{exit}^2, \text{ electrical launch energy } E_{launch} = \frac{E_k}{\eta_{sys}}, \text{ rail length } L = \frac{v_{exit}^2}{2a}, \text{ and average recharge power } P_{avg} = \frac{E_{launch}}{\tau}.$$

3.10 Model Scope and Computational Traceability

The analytical framework serves as a parametric model designed to capture the dominant physical relationships involved in electromagnetic surface launch within a lunar environment. The analysis resolves the interactions between payload characteristics, rail geometry, acceleration limits, energy delivery and storage requirements, and power system scaling, establishing a clear basis for evaluating system feasibility across a representative design space.

Certain higher-fidelity physical phenomena are intentionally abstracted within this framework, including detailed electromagnetic field distributions, rail material degradation and erosion processes, plasma interactions, structural dynamics under impulsive loading, and site-specific geotechnical behavior. These effects are recognized as important contributors to system performance and longevity and are identified as areas for targeted investigation in future development phases.

To ensure transparency and reproducibility, the computational models used in this study are provided as supplementary materials. These include system-level infrastructure and energy sizing models, payload-class trade analyses, and parametric evaluations of orbital aspects, along with the dataset for payload sizing. Together, these materials enable traceable implementations of the analytical framework and support reproducible evaluation of system-level trade-offs across the modeled design space.

- Supplementary Script S1 implements a system-level infrastructure and energy sizing model for the EMRLLS concept. The script evaluates rail length, acceleration, delivered electrical energy, resistive losses, hybrid energy storage requirements, and PV system sizing as functions of payload mass, system efficiency, and launch cadence. The model incorporates constant-acceleration kinematics, lumped electrical-to-mechanical energy efficiency, and a resistive loss approximation based on the delivered power profile.
- Supplementary Script S2 extends this analysis by explicitly evaluating the relationship between payload acceleration tolerance and required infrastructure. For a fixed payload mass, the script computes rail length, time on rail, power requirements, and energy storage as functions of allowable acceleration, illustrating the strong coupling between payload survivability constraints and system-level design drivers.
- The results of the payload-class-dependent trade study are provided as Supplementary Table S1, which reports required rail length, time on rail, peak and average power, stored energy, and PV area across representative payload classes defined by allowable acceleration (g-limit). These results are generated using the parametric framework implemented in Supplementary Scripts S1 and S2 and reflect the primary scaling relationships affecting system performance.
- A supplementary parametric analysis is provided in Supplementary Script S3, which evaluates the feasibility of injecting payloads into bounded orbital corridors accessible to downstream retrieval architectures. While orbital dynamics are only treated at a conceptual level within the main text, this analysis explores the relationship between rail exit velocity, effective acceleration, and departure angle, and evaluates resulting trajectories in terms of cumulative dwell time within a representative orbital altitude band. The results demonstrate that feasible injection conditions exist within the modeled parameter space, enabling payload delivery to accessible orbital regimes without requiring the payload canister to complete a full lunar orbit prior to interception. Detailed treatment of orbital capture, trajectory correction, and retrieval architectures is reserved for future work.

Within this defined scope, the preceding sections establish a feasibility envelope linking the system characteristics and constraints. This provides the quantitative foundation for the operational context introduced in Section 4.

4. System-Level Implications and Operational Envelope

4.1 Role Within Lunar Surface-to-Orbit Logistics

EMRLLS functions as fixed lunar surface infrastructure that facilitates sustained cargo transfer from the surface to LLO. It is intended to operate within a layered transportation architecture where different ascent methods serve distinct roles (NASA, 2020; Crawford, 2015). The system is most efficient during

periods of repetitive cargo transport demands, especially when adequate surface energy generation capacity is in place.

Similar to a rail freight terminal, EMRLLS converts surface-generated electrical energy into repeatable mass transfer events. It is particularly beneficial when cadence, throughput, and long-duration operational stability are primary concerns. In such scenarios, infrastructure scaling replaces sortie-based scaling as the dominant design driver.

4.2 Nominal Operational Cycle

The operational cycle begins with payload integration and structural verification within the launch canister. During this phase, the energy storage subsystem accumulates charge from the prime power source. Once the energy and thermal margins are achieved, the system transitions to an armed state and conducts automated health diagnostics across switching, storage, rail alignment, and control systems.

Since the architecture is pulse-dominated, energy accumulation occurs over minutes and acceleration over seconds. Upon authorization, the pulse forming and switching networks coordinate discharge into the rail segments, accelerating the payload to the required exit velocity. After launch, the payload enters a bounded LLO, where it is captured and transferred by an orbital grapppler system. Following discharge, the system enters a cooldown and recharge phase to recover thermal margins and coordinate orbital capture operations. The operational tempo is largely determined by these coupled factors. A nominal operational cycle is depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2

Electromagnetic Rail Lunar Launch System (EMRLLS) Operational Flow.

Note. Operational sequence for EMRLLS cargo transfer from surface preparation through orbital capture. The flow illustrates energy accumulation, launch execution, temporary orbital retention, and grappler-assisted retrieval. Decision gates reflect system recharge state, thermal margins, and orbital capture corridor constraints.

4.3 Throughput and Cadence Implications

The energy required for each launch is approximately 200–300 MJ. With a cadence of 30 minutes, the average recharge power ranges from 150 to 300 kW. This setup allows for approximately 48 launches per day for a 100 kg payload, corresponding to a total throughput of 4,800 kg per day from surface to orbit.

Over a lunar year (~354 Earth days), this continuous operation could facilitate the transfer of about 1,700 metric tons of mass, assuming continuous availability and manageable thermal constraints. The mass throughput is directly related to steady-state surface power generation and achievable launch cadence. As electrical generation capacity increases, cumulative mass delivery scales proportionally, provided there is adequate infrastructure to support energy storage and discharge.

In contrast to traditional sortie-based chemical ascent systems, which require a dedicated propellant mass fraction for each launch, electromagnetic launch converts continuous electrical power into repeated acceleration events. The capacity for orbital logistics hinges on available energy, launch cadence, and infrastructure durability.

4.4 Integration With Surface and Orbital Infrastructure

EMRLLS integrates naturally with ISRU nodes, surface manufacturing facilities, polar PV farms, and orbital staging platforms. Surface-produced materials such as oxygen, metals, or structural components can be transferred to orbit without requiring recurring propellant production for each launch (Anand et al., 2012).

The architecture enables the direct conversion of surplus surface energy into orbital mass transfer capability. Surface infrastructure sets limits on energy accumulation and launch cadence, while orbital systems regulate redistribution and staging.

Orbital integration imposes additional requirements beyond achieving circular velocity. Injection must place the payload into an orbit that remains dynamically stable for approximately 12–24 hours prior to natural decay or surface intersection. This duration allows for operational flexibility and enables a 2–3 hour capture window within a bounded orbital corridor. Variability in velocity and azimuth during injection determines the width of this corridor and affects the delta- v (Δv) needed for the grapppler vehicle's retrieval.

In some mission configurations, the payload canister may require a modest onboard thruster to perform small phasing adjustments to reach the designated capture window. These adjustments are expected to be minimal relative to orbital velocity but must be factored into the overall energy and mass budget. The interaction between surface injection accuracy, orbital lifetime, phasing windows, and grapppler Δv forms a complex integration challenge that extends beyond rail acceleration. Such trimming propulsion could be implemented using low-thrust gaseous propellants derived from lunar ISRU, although the specific propulsion architecture is not material to the surface launch analysis presented here.

Detailed modeling of orbital lifetime sensitivity, dispersion tolerances, phasing requirements, and capture energetics remains an active area of analysis. This study identifies these coupling constraints to better define the operational envelope for surface launch performance.

4.5 Payload Classes and Operational Segmentation

Acceleration tolerance directly shapes infrastructure design and electrical stress. Table 3 summarizes specific payload classes.

Table 3
Representative Payload Classes and Acceleration Tolerance

Class	Maximum Acceleration (gravitational tolerance)	Primary Use
Rugged cargo	40 g	Metals, regolith, structural components
Standard hardware	25 g	Tanks, mechanical systems
Instrumentation	20 g	Scientific payloads

Note. Acceleration limits reflect representative structural tolerance ranges used in the present analytical model. Actual limits depend on payload design and qualification standards.

Higher acceleration reduces rail length and corridor footprint while increasing peak electrical and structural stress. Conversely, lower acceleration extends rail length and decreases instantaneous electrical loading. Therefore, operational segmentation may include distinct rails optimized for different payload tolerance ranges, enabling infrastructure specialization without overhauling the overall design.

4.6 Operational Constraints

Sustained operations depend on several interrelated factors. Thermal rejection capacity limits the maximum launch cadence by determining how quickly the rail, switching hardware, and power electronics can dissipate heat between pulses. Rail wear and switching reliability influence long-term service life and maintenance intervals, affecting system availability. Additionally, orbital capture timing and injection dispersion introduce scheduling constraints as payloads must enter a defined orbital corridor, allowing a grapppler vehicle sufficient time to rendezvous and retrieve the payload within the designated capture window. Although electromagnetic launch energy requirements may be satisfied by available surface power generation, these integration dynamics ultimately determine the rate at which payloads can be delivered to orbit. Achievable throughput reflects the combined influence of thermal limits, hardware durability, and orbital rendezvous coordination.

4.7 Transition to Mission-Specific Analysis

The operational envelope described establishes a baseline for cadence, payload tolerance, and integration limits. For mission-specific deployment, these performance limits must align with logistics objectives. The export of regolith-derived materials, ISRU oxygen supply for propellant depots, and structural components for orbital assembly each impose specific injection accuracy, capture timing, and reliability margins.

These missions introduce further constraints on targeting accuracy, dispersion tolerance, and grapppler Δv budgets. The next analysis phase will link surface acceleration performance to orbital rendezvous mechanics and system-level logistic modeling.

5. Conclusion

This study provides an initial feasibility assessment for a rail-based electromagnetic lunar surface launch architecture based on defined engineering assumptions. The relationships between payload mass, acceleration, rail length, exit velocity, aggregate efficiency, peak power, and launch cadence were derived using a lumped-parameter analytical framework. For representative payload classes and orbital injection requirements, the electrical energy per launch lies on the order of hundreds of megajoules.

The analysis indicates that infrastructure sizing is dominated primarily by exit velocity and aggregate system efficiency. In contrast, sustainable launch cadence is often constrained by thermal rejection capacity during pulsed high-current operations. These relationships define the principal engineering drivers determining electromagnetic surface launch infrastructure.

When integrated with an orbital interception layer, this infrastructure allows steady-state electrical generation to be converted into sustained orbital mass throughput, demonstrating that rail-based electromagnetic launch can effectively facilitate high-cadence lunar surface-to-orbit logistics.

Traditionally, electromagnetic launch concepts have been viewed as large-scale mass drivers intended for either terrestrial launches or bulk lunar material export. However, the EMRLLS architecture examined here differs fundamentally in operational role and system design philosophy. Instead of functioning as a standalone launch system, it is designed as fixed lunar logistics infrastructure within a layered transportation system. This framework ensures steady-state power generation is converted into repeatable cargo transfer events to LLO, where orbital vehicles manage redistribution and staging. The system functions analogously to terrestrial freight infrastructure by emphasizing sustained throughput, operational cadence, and infrastructure durability.

In summary, the findings establish electromagnetic surface rail launch as a technically viable component of future lunar surface-to-orbit logistics. Under bounded engineering assumptions and first-order energetic, structural, and thermal constraints, the concept remains consistent with known physical limits and established pulsed-power engineering principles.

6. Future Work

This analysis sets a preliminary bounded first-order energetic and infrastructure feasibility envelope for electromagnetic surface launch logistics systems. Further refinements will enhance system performance and operational margins.

Second-order electromagnetic and structural effects warrant more detailed treatment. Factors such as spatial current density distribution, rail-armature interaction, switching rise-time dynamics, structural recoil forces, and transient structural coupling influence efficiency, degradation rates, and acceleration limits. Addressing these elements will refine the infrastructure bounds established in this study and provide improved estimates of component stress and lifespan.

Thermal modeling can also be extended beyond the steady-state radiative balance employed here. A pulse-resolved transient analysis will more fully characterize the cumulative heating of rails, switching hardware, and power electronics during repeated operations. Considerations for radiator sizing, acceptable temperature increases, and cumulative thermal effects will ultimately determine sustainable duty cycles for high-cadence operations.

A multi-variable trade framework is also being developed to assess interacting design parameters, including payload mass, acceleration tolerance, launch cadence, aggregate efficiency, and injection velocity margin. These variables create a coupled design space with nonlinear interactions that influence infrastructure scaling and operational performance. Currently, computational models implemented in MATLAB and Python are producing performance surfaces within the feasible parameter space and informing optimal infrastructure scaling.

Finally, surface launch performance must be evaluated in conjunction with orbital rendezvous and capture dynamics. Injection dispersion, trajectory shaping, acceptable velocity error, phasing windows, relative intercept velocity, and capture Δv requirements will determine targeting precision and operational margins. These interactions define the interface between surface acceleration and orbital logistics operations.

Together, these extensions will refine the engineering bounds identified in the present analysis and support continued maturation of electromagnetic surface launch architectures for lunar logistics.

References

- Anand, M., Crawford, I. A., & Balat-Powell, M., Ababades, S., van Westrenen, W., Peraudeau, G., Jaumann, R., & Seboldt, W. (2012). A brief review of chemical and mineralogical resources on the Moon. *Planetary and Space Science*, 74(1), 42–48. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pss.2012.08.012>
- Bate, R., Mueller, D., White, J., & Saylor, W. (2020). *Fundamentals of Astrodynamics* (2nd ed.). Dover.
- Bergman, T. L., Lavine, A. S., Incropera, F. P., & DeWitt, D. P. (2018). *Fundamentals of Heat and Mass Transfer* (8th ed.). Wiley.
- Crawford, I. A. (2015). Lunar resources: A review. *Progress in Physical Geography Earth and Environment*, 39(2), 137–167. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0309133314567585>
- Fair, H. D. (2007). Progress in electromagnetic launch science and technology. *IEEE Transactions on Magnetics*, 43(1), 93–98. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TMAG.2006.887596>
- Glaser, P., Scholten, F., De Rosa, D., Figuera, R. M., Oberst, J., Mazarico, E., Neumann, G. A., & Robinson, M. S. (2014). Illumination conditions at the lunar south pole using high resolution digital terrain models from LOLA. *Icarus*, 243, 78-90. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.icarus.2014.08.013>
- Heiken, G. H., Vaniman, D. T., & French, B. M. (1991). Lunar Sourcebook. *Cambridge University Press*. https://www.lpi.usra.edu/publications/books/lunar_sourcebook/pdf/LunarSourceBook.pdf
- Jordan, D. C., & Kurtz, S. R. (2012). Photovoltaic degradation rates—An analytical review. *National Renewable Energy Laboratory*. JA-5200-51664. <https://docs.nrel.gov/docs/fy12osti/51664.pdf>
- Landis, G. A., Bailey, S. G., Brinker, D. J., & Flood, D. J. (1990). Photovoltaic power for a lunar base. *Acta Astronautica*, 22, 197-203. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0094-5765\(90\)90021-C](https://doi.org/10.1016/0094-5765(90)90021-C)
- Liebfried, O. (2017). *Review of inductive pulsed power generators for railguns*. arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1701.07063>
- Mazarico, E., Neumann, G.A., Smith, D.E., Zuber, M. T., & Torrence, M. H. (2011). Illumination conditions of the lunar pole regions using LOLA topography. *Icarus*, 211(2), 1066-1081. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.icarus.2010.10.030>
- McNab, I. R. (2003). Launch to space with an electromagnetic railgun. *IEEE Transactions on Magnetics*, 39(1), 295–304. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TMAG.2002.805923>
- National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA). (2020). *NASA's Lunar Exploration Program Overview*, NP-2020-05-2853-HQ. NASA. https://permanent.fdlp.gov/websites/www.nasa.gov/sites/default/files/atoms/files/artemis_plan-20200921.pdf
- O'Neill, G. K. (1976). *The High Frontier: Human Colonies in Space*. New York: William Morrow and Company.
- O'Neill, G. K., Billingham, J., Gilbreath, W., O'Leary, B., & Gossett, B. (1979). *Space Resources and Space Settlements*. NASA SP-428. Washington, DC: NASA. <https://ntrs.nasa.gov/api/citations/19790024054/downloads/19790024054.pdf>
- Pappa, R., Rose, G., Paddock, D., & Lepsch, R. (2019). *Solar power for lunar pole missions* [PowerPoint slides]. NASA. <https://ntrs.nasa.gov/api/citations/20200000285/downloads/20200000285.pdf?>
- Rose, A., Ruppert, S., Glaser, P., & Elvis, M. (2021). *Towers on the peaks of eternal light: Quantifying the available solar power*. arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2102.11766>

Siva-Rodriguez, J., & Li, X. (2024). *Solar Power Generation Profile Estimation for Lunar Surface Solar Photovoltaic Systems*. arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2402.14783>